

Evaluating Understandability and Actionability of Artificial Intelligence in Creating a High-Quality Educational Content for Type 2 Diabetes Using Predesigned Prompts

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Abstract

Background: AI has the potential to revolutionize healthcare, with chatbots like ChatGPT emerging as practical tools for creating educational content. Type 2 diabetes has become a significant global health challenge, necessitating effective prevention and management strategies. Patient education is crucial for informed decision-making, but traditional materials often lack accessibility and engagement. **Aim:** This study aims to evaluate ChatGPT's understandability and actionability in generating high-quality educational content for type 2 diabetes using predesigned prompts. **Methods:** A qualitative exploratory design was employed to assess the content generated by ChatGPT. The Patient Educational Materials Assessment Tool (PEMAT) focused on five significant health education domains relevant to diabetes. The PEMAT assessment included 17 items for understandability and 7 for actionability, with a score of $\geq 70\%$ required to pass. **Results:** Prompts with a simple, clear instructional guideline yielded significantly higher scores than those with multiple instructions or single prompt with no addition. This indicates that focused prompt design enhances the quality of AI-generated educational content. **Conclusion:** This study demonstrates that artificial intelligence, particularly ChatGPT, has the potential to generate high-quality, understandable, and actionable educational content for patients with type 2 diabetes, when guided by simple well-structured, predesigned prompts and supported by scientific source material.

Introduction

Health education is a key strategy in disease prevention, as it promotes awareness of risk factors

And encourages the adoption of healthier habits. Through structured education campaigns, individuals can better understand preventive measures, such as

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nutrition, hygiene, personal care, and physical activity, reducing the incidence of communicable and non-communicable diseases [5].

Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus is a metabolic disorder characterized by elevated blood sugar levels due to insulin resistance or impaired insulin production. It has become one of the biggest global health challenges, with its prevalence rising significantly over recently. The continuous increase in cases underscores the importance of implementing effective measures to prevent and manage the disease

properly to reduce its impact on public health and healthcare systems. Studies have shown that diabetes education improves glycemic control and overall health outcomes. For example, a systematic review of the effect on glycemic control conducted in "Diabetes self-management education for adults with type 2 diabetes mellitus: A systematic review of the effect on glycemic control" [3], reported that diabetes self-management education (DSME) significantly reduces HbA1c levels, improves patient self-efficacy, and enhances adherence to treatment plans. Health education is pivotal in ensuring patients can make informed decisions about their diabetes care [5]. AI applications like ChatGPT and Google's Gemini exemplify advancements in natural language processing (NLP). Artificial Intelligence enables the creation of educational materials tailored to the unique needs of individuals, offering personalized learning experiences. It also provides innovative learning environments that diverge from traditional educational models, facilitating faster and more effective learning in unconventional ways. When applied to public health, AI enhances the quality of education and training and fosters the development of new methods and tools. These skills empower health professionals and practitioners to adopt behaviours and habits that equip them to address emerging health challenges in the years ahead [4].

Materials and Methods

Study Design

A qualitative exploratory design.

Data Collection Tool

Designed to evaluate understandability (how easily information can be comprehended by the intended audience) and actionability (content clearly guides individuals on what steps to take or how to apply the information) patient education materials. Its primary purpose is to assist healthcare professionals in selecting or developing adequate educational resources that facilitate patient comprehension and encourage appropriate health-related actions [7].

PEMAT is Available in Two Versions:

PEMAT-P [7], which assesses printed materials, and PEMAT- A/V, which evaluates audiovisual materials. The tool uses a structured approach to measure key

factors such as clarity of language, logical organization, use of visuals, and the extent to which the material promotes informed decision-making. By providing numerical scores, PEMAT helps identify strengths and areas for improvement, ultimately contributing to the enhancement of health education quality and patient engagement.

AI Platform

ChatGPT was selected as an AI platform example for creating health education content. It was chosen because it is the most widely used, available to everyone with a free version, and helps save time[4].

Prompts

Are instructions given to ChatGPT to elicit specific responses. They outline the context, topic, and desired format of the information or content being requested.

Prompt Development Steps

The prompts were developed through a systematic process as follows:

1-A case study for a woman with type 2 diabetes was developed: A 40-year-old woman, married with two children, who has a low educational background. She is experiencing Type 2 diabetes, deterioration of her vision, nocturnal urinary incontinence, and numbness in her hands and feet. Additionally, she suffers from recurrent abscesses in various areas of her body and has been diagnosed as obese

2- Five significant domains of health education were selected to cover the needs of this case as follows

Domain 1: Self-glucose monitoring

Domain 2: Nutritional tips

Domain 3: Foot care

Domain 4: Physical activity

Domain 5: Compliance with medical treatment

3- An evidence-based reference book covering the health education content of the five domains was chosen based on a recommendation from a health education expert.

4- Deploying four prompts for each domain as follows:

Prompt 1: Write health educational content, (giving the case and domain) without additions (single prompt).

The instruction is as follows Create health education content focused on Self-glucose monitoring (repeated for each domain) tailored for a 40-year-old woman with Type 2 diabetes. She is married with two children, has a low educational background, and faces multiple health issues, including vision deterioration, nocturnal urinary incontinence, numbness in her extremities, recurrent abscesses, and obesity. The content should highlight the critical importance of monitoring her glucose levels.

Prompt 2: Write health educational content using the attached reference "Basic Skills for Living with Diabetes"[2].

The instruction is as follows: Create health education content focused on Self-glucose monitoring (repeated

for each domain) tailored for a 40-year-old woman with Type 2 diabetes. She is married with two children, has a low educational background, and faces multiple health issues, including vision deterioration, nocturnal urinary incontinence, numbness in her extremities, recurrent abscesses, and obesity. Using the attached reference "Basic Skills for Living with Diabetes"[2]. The content should highlight the critical importance of monitoring her glucose levels.

Prompt 3: Write health educational content that considers the Patient Education Materials Assessment Tool (PEMAT). The instruction is as follows:

Create health education content focused on Self-glucose monitoring (repeated for each domain) tailored for a 40-year-old woman with Type 2 diabetes. She is married with two children, has a low educational background, and faces multiple health issues, including vision deterioration, nocturnal urinary incontinence, numbness in her extremities, recurrent abscesses, and obesity. That considers the PEMAT tool. The content should highlight the critical importance of monitoring her glucose levels.

Prompt 4: Write health educational content using the attached reference "Basic Skills for Living" with Diabetes" together with the PEMAT tool. The instruction is as follows: Create health education content focused on the domain (repeated for each domain) tailored for a 40-year-old woman with Type 2 diabetes. She is married with two children, has a low educational background, and faces multiple health issues, including vision deterioration, nocturnal urinary incontinence, numbness in her extremities, recurrent abscesses, and obesity. Using the attached reference [2], consider the PEMAT Tool. The content should highlight the critical importance of monitoring her glucose levels.

5-The generated content provided by the ChatGPT of all prompts for all domains will be compared to the content recommended evidence reference and assessed using the PEMAT Tool.

Data Analysis

The responses generated by ChatGPT have been evaluated using the PEMAT Tool.

PEMAT tool consists of 24 items, 17 items are used to assess the understandability domain of the content material and seven items are used to assess the actionability domain.

Each of the 24 items of the PEMAT tool was rated as "Agree=1", "Disagree=0", or "Not Applicable=N/A", based on the authors' careful review.

The authors think like a patient through the evaluation of ChatGPT content to ensure that the content is clear and understandable. Additional guidance for scoring:

- Use "Agree" if the characteristic was present 80-100% of the time.

- If the content is unclear, missing, or weak, use "Disagree."
- No items were skipped unless "N/A" was explicitly allowed.
- Judgments were based solely on the content material itself.
- Each item was rated independently to avoid bias.

Calculate Scores

Two scores were calculated per material: one for understandability and one for actionability.

-To assess understandability: add all "Agree" points → divide by total rated items (excluding N/A) → multiply by 100 (Example: 12 Agree, 3 Disagree, 1 N/A → $12 \div 15 = 0.8 \rightarrow 80\%$)

-The exact calculation process is used to assess actionability.

Interpretation of the Scores

The final score for each domain was recorded as "pass" or "fail", based on the cutoff score of $\geq 70\%$, established by the PEMAT criteria. Higher scores reflect better clarity and usefulness.

Ethical Considerations

This research has an ethical approval (IRB Number: 25-0015) which was obtained from Princess Nourah Bint Abdulrahman University.

This research is expected to improve health education content related to Type 2 diabetes.

The research adheres to scientific principles that ensure the content is evidence-based and relevant.

By conducting appropriate data collection and analysis and using findings responsibly, authors can ensure that their work is both ethically sound and methodologically rigorous.

Results

The findings of this research on the application of artificial Intelligence in content generation show the capabilities and the efficiency of AI-generated output premised on specific pre-designed prompts.

Figure 1 displays the PEMAT understandability scores for ChatGPT prompts across various domains. In Domain 1 (Self-Glucose Monitoring), single prompt generated without additions received a score of 76%, the lowest among all prompts. However, when a reference book was added, the score improved to 91.6%, with all prompts in this domain surpassing the cutoff (70%). In Domain 2 (Nutritional Tips), prompts adding a reference book and those following PEMAT guidelines both achieved a score of 90.9%. The combination of a reference book and PEMAT slightly decreased the score to 89.6%. Domain 3 (Foot Care) recorded the lowest score of 69.2% for single prompt without additions, failing to meet the cutoff score (70%). In contrast, prompts using the PEMAT guidelines and those that combined both the reference book and PEMAT surpassed the cutoff score (83.3%). In Domain 4

(Physical Activity), all prompts met the cutoff score. Prompt 3, which utilized the PEMAT tool, achieved an impressive score of 93.3%, while prompt 1 (without additions) and prompt 2 (adding a reference book) both scored the same (83.3%). Finally, in domain 5 (Physical

Activity), both prompt 1 (without additions) and prompt 4 (using a reference book and PEMAT tool) scored the same (76%). However, Prompt 3 score (using the PEMAT tool) improved to 90.9%, with all prompts exceeding the cutoff score.

Figure 1: PEMAT Understandability Score for ChatGPT-Prompts across Different Domains

Figure 2: PEMAT Actionability Score for ChatGPT-Prompts across Different Domains

Figure 2 presents the PEMAT actionability scores for ChatGPT-generated prompts across various case domains. In domain 1 (Self-Glucose Monitoring), prompts created using both the reference book and the PEMAT tool scored 60%, falling below the actionability cutoff (70%). In contrast, prompt 2, which used only a reference book, achieved the maximum score (100%). Additionally, prompt 1 and prompt 3, each received a

score of 80%, meeting the cutoff and indicating acceptable actionability. In Domain 2 (Nutritional Tips), both prompt 2, which used a reference book, and prompt 3, which followed the PEMAT guidelines, achieved the maximum score (100%). In contrast, prompt 1 (single, without additions), and prompt 4 (adding both a reference book and the PEMAT tool) received the lowest score of 75%. In domain 3 (Foot

Care), prompt 1 (single, no additions), prompt 2 (adding a reference book), and prompt 3 (adding PEMAT guidelines) each scored 60%, which means failing to meet the 10actionability cutoff score (70%). Only prompt 4, which combined both a reference book and the PEMAT tool, achieved the cutoff score (80%), indicating acceptable actionability. In domain 4 (Physical Activity), prompts 1, 2, and 4 each scored 60%, which did not meet the actionability cutoff score (70%). Only prompt 3, which was developed using PEMAT

guidelines, achieved a score of 80%, thereby meeting the cutoff score for acceptable actionability. In domain 5 (Physical Activity), both prompt 1 (generated without additions) and prompt 2 (using a reference book) scored 60%, falling below the actionability cutoff score. Notably, prompt 3, which used the PEMAT guidelines, received the lowest score of 50% across all prompts. Prompt 4 was the only prompt in this domain to meet the cutoff score, with a score of 80%, indicating acceptable actionability.

Figure 3: Mean Understandability Score of the Content Material (%) Using PEMAT Tool

Figure 3 shows the mean understandability score (%) using the PEMAT Tool. Prompt 1 (without additions) gave a mean score of 78%, indicating moderate understandability. Prompt 2 (using reference book) gave a mean score of 86.76%, demonstrating that the reference book significantly enhanced clarity. Prompt 3 (using the PEMAT tool) achieved the highest mean

score of 88.4%, making it the most effective method for improving understandability. Prompt 4 (combining references book and the PEMAT tool) gave a mean score of 81.08%, which is above the cutoff score but lower than the mean scores in prompt 2 and prompt 3, suggesting that the PEMAT tool is slightly more effective when used solely.

Figure 4: Mean Actionability Score for Content Material (%) Using PEMAT Tool

Figure 4 shows the mean actionability score (%) using the PEMAT Tool. Neither prompt 1 (without additions)

nor prompt 2 (using a reference book) mean score passed the cutoff score(70%) as each of them gave a

mean score of 67%, indicating that the content is not fully actionable. Prompt 3 (Using PEMAT Tool) has a 74% mean score passing the cutoff score, indicating that the PEMAT tool significantly improves actionability. Prompt 4 (combined references book and (PEMAT Tool) gave a 71% mean score, exceeding the cutoff score, suggesting that combining the reference book and PEMAT tool provides some improvement but is still not as effective as using the PEMAT tool alone (74%).

Discussion

This study aims to evaluate artificial Intelligence in creating understandable and actionable high-quality educational content for type 2 diabetes as a case study using pre-designed prompts. ChatGPT was selected as an example of an artificial Intelligence platform.

The study findings demonstrate the potential of ChatGPT as an artificial Intelligence as a valuable tool for generating high-quality, understandable, and actionable patient education materials related to type 2 diabetes.

In comparison with the study titled "Assessing the Quality of Patient Education Materials on Cardiac Catheterization from Artificial Intelligence Chatbots" [8], which utilized the PEMAT tool to assess material quality, ChatGPT achieved 100% in the understandability aspect and 75% in the actionability aspect. In the current study, prompt 1 (single with no addition) recorded scores of 78% for understandability and 67% for actionability. This discrepancy highlights ChatGPT's limitation in consistently producing the same content when given identical instructions repeatedly.

Figure 3 has shown that the understandability scores for all prompts has marked an improvement over the passing cutoff score (70%). Figure 3 has shown that the understandability scores for all prompts have a marked improvement over the passing cutoff score (70%). Prompt 2 (adding a reference book) and prompt 3 (adding PEMAT toll) achieved the highest scores of 86.7% and 88.4% respectively. Prompt 4, which is a combined one (including the PEMAT tool and the reference book), resulted in a slightly lower score of 81.1%. Prompt 1 (single with no addition) scored the lowest among all the prompts (78%). These results underscore that ChatGPT performs better in producing high quality content when supplied with guidelines (as PEMAT tool) or scientific reference.

A recent study titled "Exploring the ability of ChatGPT to create quality patient education resources about kidney transplant"[6] found that ChatGPT generated content that was both easily comprehensible and medically accurate when used simple instruction. In the current study, ChatGPT produced the highest-scoring content in terms of understandability (86.7% with the reference book and 88.4% with PEMAT tool) when given

simple, non-combined instructions. This concludes the importance of prompt design simplicity in assessing understandability of ChatGPT content.

Regarding actionability, in figure 4, ChatGPT-generated materials received 67% scores on the PEMAT actionability items. Specifically, both Prompt 1 and Prompt 2 scored 67%, which is below the passing cutoff score (70%), resulting in a failure to meet actionability criteria. In contrast, Prompt 3 achieved a score of 74%, and Prompt 4 scored 71%, just passing the cutoff score (70%). These results indicate that while the materials are relatively easy to understand, they require improvements to provide clear and applicable guidance, enabling users to take relevant health-related actions based on the given information.

Conclusion

This study demonstrates that artificial intelligence, particularly ChatGPT, has the potential to generate high-quality, understandable, and actionable educational content for patients with type 2 diabetes, when guided by simple well-structured, predesigned prompts and supported by scientific source material.

Acknowledgement

Not applicable

Conflict of Interests

Authors declare no conflict of interest.

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